

Performance Assessment of Compressive Strength Property of Concrete Made with Hong Soybeans Hull Ash and Groundnuts Shell Ash in the Production of Ternary Concrete

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Abstract:

Rapid urbanization through infrastructural development has resulted in depletion of natural resources leading to effects of flooding, global warming with incidents of health issues. A more ecofriendly way to solve this problem is through the adoption, use and invention of more ecofriendly concrete composite. Therefore, this research investigated the effect of replacing blended mix of soybeans hull ash (SBHA) and groundnuts shell ash (GSA) in concrete production. A total of 108 cubes of 100mm x 100mm x 150mm were cast. The study specifically determined the physical and chemical properties of Soybean hull ash and groundnut shell ash, setting time and the compressive behavior of the concrete cubes. 6 mixes were produced with identities T0, T10, T20, T30, T40 and T50, the cubes were cured

in water at 7, 14, 28 56, 90 and 180 days. The result shows an increase in compressive strength with increase in days of hydration. On 28 days curing, the strength of the ternary composites cured in water were in the range of 83% to 87% strength of the control cubes. The compressive strengths of the ternary concrete at 28 days were T0: 25.5N/mm², T10: 21.1N/mm², T20: 22.2N/mm², T30: 24.2N/mm², T40: 22.2N/mm² and T50: 24.3N/mm² indicating a slow level of formation of SiO₂ at the early stage of curing however at a latter age of 56 days curing there was a rapid increment in the compressive strength with all the concrete cubes attaining higher strength than the control concrete cubes while T50 possessed the highest compressive strength of 27.5N/mm². Therefore, this study recommends T50 composing of 80%OPC + 12.5 %SBHA + 7.5% GSA for use for structural elements in Hong, LGA Adamawa for construction purposes.

Keywords: *Compressive, Groundnuts, Performance, Soybeans, Ternary composites, Workability.*

Introduction

Today, there is need to adopt local resources to replace cement if we want to overcome the present crisis of provision of houses and the adverse effects cement production has on

natural resources depletion and human health for sustainable purposes (Soji, et al., 2020). Studies, by Isa (2016); Maxwell and Job (2016); Usman et al. (2020) posits that the construction industry relies heavily on cement for its operations in the development of shelter and

other infrastructural facilities. However, due to the high cost of cement, it has become extremely difficult for majority of people to own their own houses, this has resulted in the populace cutting corners through use of substandard materials that are not in line with specifications in order to own a shelter over their heads leading to many collapses of structures as noticed recently across cities in Nigeria, in an attempt to reduce costs (Soji, et al. 2020; Kabir, et al.; 2020; Usman, et al. 2020). A way out of this problem is either through reducing the energy costs inherent in cement production during the burning of clinker, or by increasing the production of the composite cement (Maxwell and Job, 2016). The latter usually involves replacing a proportion of the clinker-high calorie consuming portion by other products that are suitable, and do not require further heat treatment (Isa, 2016; Kabir, et al. 2020). These products are usually referred to as pozzolanas (Maxwell, et al. 2016).

Pozzolana has been described by different authors (Usman, et al. 2020; Soji, et al. 2020; Nwankwo and Job, 2014; Maxwell, 2015) as a siliceous/aluminous material which in itself possesses little or no cementitious value, but in the presence of moisture will chemically react with calcium hydroxide or lime at ordinary temperatures to form compounds possessing cementitious properties in finely divided form. However, a more precise definition of pozzolana refers to siliceous or aluminous material that, when combine with lime, react chemically to form compounds possessing cementitious properties. These materials are often used as supplementary cementitious material (SCM) in construction to enhance the strength and durability of concrete (Usman, et al., 2020). They include fly ash, burnt clay, calcined diatomaceous earth, volcanic ash, etc (Soji, et al., 2020; Soji, et al., 2022, Isa, 2016).

The technical advantage of replacing Portland cement with pozzolanas is the modification of the mechanical properties of the fresh and hardened concrete (Maxwell and Job, 2016). This includes slower rate of setting and hardening, lower heat of hydration, improved durability in acidic environments and higher ultimate strength (Maxwell, et al., 2016). Since

Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) is typically the most expensive constituent of concrete, the replacement of some proportion with pozzolanas such as the combined usage Soybean Hull ash (SBHA) and Groundnuts Shell Ash (GSA) may improve cement or concrete affordability particularly for low-cost housing in developing countries like Nigeria and in particular in Hong LGA of Adamawa State where most of the populace are peasant farmers.

The use of Soybean Hull ash (SBHA) and Groundnut Shell Ash (GSA) may contribute not only to the production of concrete of a higher quality and lower cost but also the reduction of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emission from the production of cement (Alabadan, et al., 2022). Furthermore, the partial replacement of cement with combined SBHA and GSA may also result in lower energy consumption associated with the production of cement and further solve problems arising from disposal of agricultural wastes like Soybeans hull, groundnuts shell, rice husks etc (Maxwell, 2015; Joseph, 2015; Zakka, et al., 2015). Soybeans hull ash and groundnuts shell ash are agricultural wastes and obtained from the incineration of Soybeans shell (SBS) and Groundnuts Shell (GS) respectively (Ahsan and Hossain, 2018). Furthermore, Pancewska and Wilińska (2020) posits that these wastes are usually pound in drums or hit with sticks and the shells sieved to obtain the needed raw material. Works by Maxwell, et al. (2016) documented that the seed of the Soybeans hull ash make up 92% by weight of the plant while the hull makes about 8% of the plant, for the seed of the groundnuts shell ash make up 90% by weight of the plant while the hull makes about 10% of the plant (Maxwell and Job, 2016). These materials play important roles when added to Portland cement, because they usually increase the mechanical strength and durability of concrete structures (Kefin and Adole, 2006). These Waste Agricultural Biomass (WAB) which includes rice husks, saw dust, palm kernel shells, locust beans pods, Millet husks, Soybeans hull e.t.c constitutes precious resource which can be useable as a recycled materials and or energy to reduce pressure on natural resources and ensures

sustainability for future generation (Maxwell et al., 2016).

Studies by scholars across Nigeria have shown that such agricultural wastes, play important roles when added to Portland cement because they tend to increase the compressive, mechanical strength and durability of the composite concrete structures and check the adverse effect of cracks on concrete structures (Usman, et al., 2020; Soji, et al., 2022). For instance, Maxwell and Job (2016) studied the combined performance of Rice husk Ash, Groundnut shell ash and Sugar Cane bagasse ash and reported that the compressive strength of all the cubes increase with increased in the days of curing and that all the concrete cubes attained the compressive strength of 52 – 75% of their 28-day strength at 3 days of curing in water. Also, Maxwell, et al. (2016), documented an increase in the compressive strength of Sugar Cane bagasse and Rice hush ash when used to substitute cement in concrete production up to 40% replacement level. Furthermore, Ghanan and Hilmi (2010) who carried out a similar work on properties of rice husk ash and its use as cement replacement material posits an increase in compressive strength of the concrete at a very appreciable level at a latter day of curing when compared with the control cubes. In an effort by Okala, et al. (2016) on the compressive strength property of pigeon pod ash (PPPA) concrete, the researchers concludes that inclusion of PPPA into concrete production does not affect the structural integrity of concrete in terms of strength as the compressive strength continued to increase with age of curing in water. The study therefore recommends concrete with optimum Pigeon Pea Pod Ash (PPPA) replacement of 20% as suitable for structural elements. Also, Yusuf (2018) reported that a synergetic effect of Rice husk ash and saw dust ash has proven compressive integrity in terms of improved performance. The study concludes that Rice husk ash and saw dust ash, are a promising combined supplementary construction material that can be used for the production of concrete which can conveniently serve as structural elements for construction purposes. Soybeans hull ash and Groundnuts shell ash could be

cheaper options, if found to be mechanically suitable and owing to the relative abundance of the raw material even as they are readily farmed and cultivated in Hong LGA, Adamawa State. This will check the issues of cracks and differential settlements noticed in some communities of Hong LGA Adamawa State as well as serve as a source of income to the indigenes whom are mostly farmers if the wastes are sold out for proper disposal instead of the usual disposal by uncontrolled burning. Based on the foregoing, this research focused on inventing new environmentally friendly pozzolan cement and also to assure its potency for building construction works in Hong LGA, Adamawa State.

Therefore, the specific objectives of this study include: to determine the physical and the chemical properties of Soybeans Hull Ash and Groundnuts Shell Ash, to establish the optimum amount or percentage substitution levels between Soybeans Hull Ash and Groundnuts Shell Ash in the cement matrix and to evaluate the compressive strength of the cubes produced with varying percentage replacement of Soybeans Hull Ash and Groundnuts Shell Ash as replacement of cement.

Materials

The ordinary Portland cement (Ashaka brand, Nigeria, specific gravity: 3.15) conforming to NIS 444–1 (Standard Organization of Nigeria, 2014) was used in this study. The materials used in this study were the conventional materials for concrete production these include cement, water, fine and coarse aggregates, as well as the Soybeans hull and Groundnuts shell which were used as supplementary cementitious material (SCMs).

The SBHA and GSA were obtained from Hong LGA, Adamawa state, Nigeria and thermally processed in a furnace at the temperature of 600°C for 3 hours to ash this was to ensure proper combustion of the ash to easily get a finely divided powder (The physical properties obtained of the SBHA, were specific gravity: 2.29, bulk density: 890 kg/m³ and moisture content: 1.45%), for the Groundnuts Shell Ash

(The physical properties obtained of the GSA, were specific gravity: 1.52, bulk density: 461 kg/m³ and moisture content: 0.42%) this was allowed to cool to room temperature (27 degree centigrade) before being sieved using BS sieve size (75µm). Thereafter, X-ray fluorescence was performed on the metakaolin sample to determine its chemical composition. The XRF was done at PRODA Enugu State using Energy Dispersive X-ray Fluorescence (EDXRF) spectrometer manufactured by PANalytical in Netherlands of model “Minipal 4” version PW 4030 (Tables 1 and 2) respectively.

The Sand was collected from Benue River in Yola, Nigeria (and passing through BS 4.75mm

sieve size, with specific gravity: 2.67, bulk density: 1,628.0 kg/m³ and moisture content: 2.45%) was used as fine aggregate. Crushed granite (with maximum size of 12 mm, specific gravity of 2.75, moisture content of 1.25% and bulk density of 1895.0 kg/m³) was used as coarse aggregate. Portable drinking water with a pH value of 6.5 was used for concrete mix and curing. Since the (SiO₂ + Al₂O₃ + MgO) is less than the stipulated above 70% combined content of such oxides in the GSA. Therefore, the GSA can be classed a class F pozzolana having not satisfy the requirements for a good pozzolana. However, the GSA served as a good retarding pozzolana in this research (Isa, 2016).

Figure 1. Particle Size Distribution for Aggregates

Methodology

The methodology adopted for this research work is the experimental laboratory investigations. The soybeans hull and Groundnut Shell used for this research work was sourced from Hong LGA and its environs in Adamawa state of Nigeria. Consequently, these husks were transported in Bags to the National Steel Raw Material Exploration Agency (NSRMEA) in Kaduna, Kaduna State for the burning and grinding of the ash. 10kg each of the

ash samples was taking to PRODA in Enugu for the physical and chemical characterization. Samples of soybean hull ash and groundnut shell ash were collected in separate bags and taken to the concrete and structural laboratory of the Department of Building, Modibbo Adama University Yola for the test proper. The sieve analysis was carried out on the ashes at Soil mechanics laboratory of the Department of Building, Modibbo Adama University Yola to ascertain the particle sizes of the soybean ash

and groundnut shell ash as pozzolanic materials. The sieve analysis test was also conducted on the sourced samples of sharp sand and gravels (See Figure 1).

Figure 2. Some of the Cast Cubes

Plate 2: Some Weigh Concrete Cubes Ready for Compressive Strength Test

Figure 4. Universal Compressive Strength Testing Machine Used for Cubes Cast

Figure 5. A Ternary Concrete Cube Showing Failure under Compression

For the purpose of this study cement was substituted with varying percentages of the fine powdery synergetic composition of SBHA and GSA at a replacement level between 0 and 20% adopted from the recommendation of works by (Soji, et al., 2020; Maxwell and Job, 2016; Joseph, 2015). 108 cubes were produced using 100mm x 100mm x 100mm cube steel moulds (Figure 2 and 3). Mix ratio of 1: 2: 4 was adopted for the production of concrete cubes with the cement partially replaced by Soybeans hull ash and Groundnuts shell ash in varied percentage of its weight as follows (T0 represents 100 % OPC + 0 % SBHA + 0 % GSA as control, T10 represents 80 % OPC + 15 % SBHA + 5 % GSA, T20 represents 80% OPC + 5 % SBHA + 15 % GSA, T30 represents 80 % OPC + 10 % SBHA + 10 % GSA, T40 represents 85 % OPC + 7.5 % SBHA + 12.5 % GSA and T50 represents 80 % OPC + 12.5 % SBHA + 7.5 % GSA). After which the workability of each mix was assessed using the slump. The cubes 3 samples each were cast (some samples shown in Figure 2) were then cured under room temperature in water for 7, 14 and 28, 56, 90 and 180 days before the determination of the compression test on each sample of the cubes at established day of curing. The weights of the samples were taken using the electrically operated weighing balance. The universal testing machine, an electrically operated compressive strength machine was use to obtain the failure loads in kilo Newton. The average failure loads

were used to obtain the universal compressive strength testing machine shown in (Figure 4 and Figure 5).

Results

Chemical composition

Tables 1 and 2 shows the chemical composition of the SBHA and GSA used respectively in this study respectively. The SBHA had a combined composition of $\text{SiO}_2 + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{MgO}$ which is

above 70% which is universally acceptable as a good pozzolana while the GSA with a combine proportion of $\text{SiO}_2 + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{MgO}$ fall less than the accepted level of a good pozzolana but as a Class F pozzolana it can be used as a retarding pozzolan as posited by Isa (2016). Other constituents such as Cr_2O_3 , ZnO etc were detected but in a very negligible level while other were not detected at all eg PbO , CuO etc this is as would be expected because not all pozzolanas have same chemical compositions (Neville, *et al.*, 1987).

Table 1. Chemical Composition of SBHA

Oxides	Al_2O_3	SiO_2	SO_3	K_2O	CaO	V_2O_5
Mass (%)	0.89	81.41	-	1.92	3.18	-
Oxides	Fe_2O_3	TiO	ZnO	Cr_2O_3	MnO	LOI
Mass (%)	1.08	0.47	0.01	0.02	0.84	5.06

Table 2. Chemical Composition of GSA

Oxides	Al_2O_3	SiO_2	SO_3	K_2O	CaO	V_2O_5
Mass (%)	2.13	40.06	6.0	12.89	3.18	-
Oxides	Fe_2O_3	TiO	ZnO	Cr_2O_3	MnO	LOI
Mass (%)	9.99	7.38	0.01	0.01	0.51	9.27

Workability

Slump Results

From the study, it was found that the slump generally reduced as the pozzolana content increased. The results indicate a reduction from 100mm of the control mix ratio 1:2:4 to 77mm about 0.23% for T50 containing (80OPC+12.5SBHA+7.5GSA). The higher the replacement of cement by the ash increases water demand and therefore for given water cement ratio and cement content, this reduces workability as justified by Yusuf (2008). According to Isa (2016), the reduction in slump increase may also be a consequence of increased amount of silica dissolving into solution. From the study, it was found that the silica-lime reaction requires more water in addition to water required during hydration of cement as opined by Nwankwo and Job (2014), while the immediate workability decreases, the adsorbed water might be partially released during the hardening process (Soji, *et al.*, 2021). This phenomenon may be attributed to the physical

characteristics of the pozzolana i.e., particle size distribution, specific gravity and the of fineness of the particles of the pozzolans as reported by Ambrose, *et al.* (2023); Cordeiro, *et al.* (2012). The slump test was performed on the fresh concrete to determine its workability (BS EN 12350: 2019) (Usman, *et al.* 2020)

Compaction factor

The compaction factor reduces as the percentage of the cement replacement increases. T0, T10, T20, T30, T40 and T50 of concrete mix proportion 1:2:4 has compacting factor results of 0.956mm, 0.925mm, 0.921mm, 0.914mm, 0.909mm and 0.901 respectively within the percentage range of 0.69 and 1%. This indicates that the concrete becomes less workable with increase in the cement replacement and increase the water – cement ratio as would be expected because more of the paste goes into solution rapidly indicating that extra water is required to make the mix more workable as argued by Neville, *et al.* (1987).

Setting time

The initial and the final setting time test was performed on both plain cement pastes and those having SBHA and GSA content. Results of the initial and final setting time of the cement pastes are presented in Table 3. The result show that due to the high pace of the evaporation of heat from the cementitious paste due to low cement content. The initial setting time of the control cubes was faster than the ternary concrete initially. However, it becomes lower as

the concrete sets, this corresponds to the opinion of Nwankwo, et al. (2014) which established that the reaction between cement and water is exothermic and greater amount of heat would be evolved because of the high cement paste therefore the pace of induced heat evaporation will be slow (Ahmadi, et al., 2007; Prasanphan, et al. 2022; Elinna, et al., 2004; Yusuf 2012). However, the setting time were within the recommended range for ordinary Portland cement paste of 45 minutes to 12 hours by ASTM C39 (2003).

Table 3. Setting Time of Cement Paste

Slump	Compacting Factor (mm)	Setting time of Cement Paste (mins)	
		Initial setting time	Final setting time
T0 100	0.956	75	115
T0 75	0.925	50	120
T0 73	0.921	55	130
T0 71	0.941	60	135
T0 69	0.909	65	155
T0 68	0.901	75	160

Chemical Composition and Mix Design

Table 4 shows the Summary of mass of constituents per cubic metre of concrete for the 1:2:4 mix proportions. The mix proportion for the concrete cubes' ingredient are shown in Table 4. The SBHA and GSA as cement replacement material was evaluated (with control

mix T0, T10, T20, T30, T40, and T50). These 6 types of specimens were designed and the various composition of the materials presented in Table 4. Except for the varying proportion of the Cement, and the SCMs, all other ingredients such as the FA, CA and Water content remains equal in each specimen.

Table 4. Constituents of Materials per Cubic Meter

	Cement (kg)	SBHA (kg)	GSA (kg)	FA (kg)	CA (kg)	Water (kg)
T0	294	-	-	620	1200	145
T10	235	44	15	620	1200	145
T20	235	29.5	29.5	620	1200	145
T30	235	15	44	620	1200	145
T40	235	37	22	620	1200	145
T50	235	22	37	620	1200	145

Note: Where T = Ternary mix of Cement + Soy bean hulls (SCBA) + Groundnuts Shell Ash (GSA)

Discussion

Compressive Strength of the Ternary Composites

Table 5 and Figures 6 and 7 show the compressive strengths of the cubes with the different mix proportions increased with curing

age. The result generally shows an increase in compressive strength with increase in days of hydration. At 28 days of hydration the compressive strength of the specimen T30 and specimen T50 attained an Fcu of (24.2N/mm²) and (24.3N/mm²) respectively which were close to the control specimen with compressive

strength of 25.4N/mm². The lower values of the compressive strength of the blended mixture at early time of hydration constitute a percentage ranging from 54% to 83% in the mixture; this may be due to the reduction in cement content and the slow dissolution of silica as reported by (Olutuge, Buari, and Adeleke 2013; Nwankwo and Job (2014) leading to lower pozzolanic activity at the early ages of curing which implies that though the results showed that the compressive strengths of the cubes with the different mix proportions increase with curing age, the values are lower in the case of specimens with the pozzolanic blends at early age (Okala, et al., 2016). However, the compressive strength after 28 days of hydration of the ternary concrete is quite comparable with that of the control with an improvement within the range of 83% to 96% of the compressive strength. The reason may be due to more of silica going into solution and so forms additional amount of calcium silicate hydrate (CSH), which leads to strength enhancement in the long time as reported by (Afolayan, et al. 2018; Yusuf 2012). The compressive strength of the control specimen mix (T0) proportion increased from 20.65 N/mm² at 7days curing age to 25.4N/mm² and 26.5N/mm² at 28days and 90days curing ages respectively, indicating about 77% increase showing a positive improvement in the compressive strength. T10 with strength of 11.1N/mm², 21.9N/mm² and 26.6N/mm² at 7days, 28days and 180 days curing respectively, shows the strength development (F_c) ratio (28/7) as 1.97 which is higher than the desirable ratio of 1.25 (Neville, et al., 1987). The high ratio

may be attributed to the quick formation of Calcium – Silicate – Hydrate (CSH) between 7 days and 28 days curing age. Similarly, T30 with strength of 14.8N/mm², 24.2N/mm² and 26.7 N/mm² at 7days, 28days and 180days of curing respectively, shows the strength development (F_c) ratio (28/7) obtained as 1.63 which is above the desirable ratio of 1.25(Neville, et al., 1987). The high ratio may also be due to the moderate formation of Calcium – Silicate – Hydrate (CSH) between 7- and 28-days curing age. Another reason may be due to more of silica from the SBHA and GSA going into solution which forms additional amount of calcium silicate hydrate (CSH) that leads to strength enhancement in the long time as reported by Zakka, et al. (2015) and Yusuf (2012). While T50 with strength of 17.1N/mm², 24.3N/mm² and 27.5 N/mm² at 7days, 28days and 180days of curing respectively. The strength development (F_c) ratio (28/7) was obtained as 1.43 which was also above the desirable ratio of 1.25. It is to note that, though the (F_c) ratio was lower than that of T10 and T30, but with appreciable strength increment which may be due to the binding phase of the pozzolana concrete (Ahmadi, et al., 2007). Furthermore, T50 having more strength than T0 at 56, 90 and 180 days of curing can be used as a partial substitute to cement. Also, at 28 days curing all the mix replacement achieved an appreciable strength and can be used in the production of structural concrete with T50 containing (80%OPC+12.5%SBHA+7.5%GSA) concrete exhibiting the best satisfactory performance.

Table 5 Compressive Strength of the Ternary Cubes in N/mm²

	7 days	14 days	28 days	56 days	90 days	180 days
T0	20.5	21.4	25.4	25.6	26.1	26.5
T10	11.1	13.8	21.1	25.3	25.8	26.6
T20	12.5	12.7	22.1	25.8	26.4	26.8
T30	14.8	15.5	24.2	26.3	26.4	26.7
T40	12.4	12.5	22.2	25.8	26.7	26.9
T50	17.1	19.3	24.3	26.7	27.2	27.5

Figure 6 shows the graphical representation of the increase in strength of the concrete mixes in this study by implication the Ternary composite concrete T10 has the least strength development

of 26.8N/mm² while T50 has the optimal performance strength development of 27.5/mm².

Figure 6. Compressive Strength of the Ternary Composites

Figure 7. The Compressive Strength of SBSA/GSA Ternary Concrete

Figure 7 shows the pictorial bar chart view of the increase in strength at the early age of curing. Clearly, it can be seen that at the initial stage (7 –

28 days curing) the control cubes T10 gain more strength due to the fast formation of SiO_2 at the early stage. However, after 56 – 180 days curing

all the ternary cubes possessed more strength than the control, which may be due to the rapid formation of the SiO₂ which leads to a more C-S-H binder phase as reported by Neville, *et al.* (1987).

Conclusion

Soy beans hull sourced from Hong LGA Adamawa State was found a good pozzolana having satisfied the requirement of ASTM C618 (2000), however the Groundnuts shell sourced from Hong LGA Adamawa State North – Eastern, does not satisfy the requirement of ASTM C618 (2000) but can be used as a retarding pozzolana (Class F pozzolan). The study found that ternary composites containing higher content of Soy beans hull ash tend to produce composite with more strength than those with higher content of Groundnuts shell ash. The initial and final setting times of the all the ternary composites falls within the recommended limits of 45 minutes to 10 hours as specified by ASTM - C150(1994). There was generally an increase in both compressive strength cubes as the hydration period increases. As more of the silica (SiO₂) from the Soy beans hull ash and Groundnuts shell ash. goes into solution they tend to produce a 100% binder phase of calcium silicate hydrate (C-S-H) as compared to the 75% binder phase of calcium silicate hydrate (C-S-H) formed by the non – pozzolana concrete at the same day of curing. At 28 days curing, all the ternary composites achieved appreciable strength to be use as load bearing members in structures. Therefore, this study concludes that Ternary composite, T50 composing of (80%OPC + 12.5%SBSA + 7.5GSA) is recommended for use as structural member in compressions having satisfied the structural performance and attained the required characteristics strength within the specified study area.

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Declaration

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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